

Appendix 1. Frameworks in field of WM

Ref.	Topic	Data source	Methods	Features	Stakeholders	Testing
[6]	assessment of the performance of integrated municipal solid waste management	model, that consists of all major stages in solid waste management and its environmental impact	fuzzy MACBETH multi-criteria decision-making model used to investigate the uncertainties and inefficiencies associated with solid waste management systems	comparative assessment of the performance of integrated municipal solid waste management, investigates the uncertainties and inefficiencies associated with solid waste management systems	authorities	was examined in the South European region
[10]	waste to energy (WTE) resource planning	real-world data set obtained from MSW stations on the European side of Istanbul, Turkey	machine learning	waste to energy (WTE) resource planning predict the amount of municipal solid waste (MSW) to be used for smart energy management systems	authorities	lab testing, simulation based on real-world data
[11]	Construction waste recycling	adopting the qualitative research methods of case study, site visits and semi-structured interviews in Shenzhen, China	decision-support framework to help plan on-site and off-site construction waste recycling	plan on-site and off-site construction waste recycling	authorities	no
[16]	monitor violations prior to the waste collection process	IoT-sensors	IoT-sensors for real-time monitoring sources of violations prior to the waste collection process	help municipalities, local governments or waste management companies to monitor in real-time sources of	authorities and companies	no

				violations prior to the waste collection process		
[12]	industrial waste	case study	Modified Analytical Hierarchy Process (AHP) was applied as a MCDA approach for structuring complex problems and assisting decision makers to choose the best alternative among a discrete set of scenarios. Differing preferences of the stakeholders were resolved by synthesizing the conflicting weightings in the beginning of the analysis. Life-Cycle Assessment (LCA) was used to evaluate the social-ecological impacts of emissions, energy demand and impact to human health.	framework for analysis of alternative cover scenarios with multiple-criteria decision analysis (MCDA) applied for the purpose	authorities	no
[13]	Agriculture and poultry waste: automated WM, waste minimization	IoT-sensors	IoT-sensors for real-time monitoring	automated WM, waste minimization	agriculture related authorities and companies	no
[6]	assessment of the performance of integrated municipal solid waste management	data obtained from the different sectors of the integrated solid waste management system in the European countries located in its southern	the fuzzy MACBETH multi-criteria decision-making model used to investigate the uncertainties and inefficiencies associated with solid waste management systems	comparative assessment of the performance of integrated municipal solid waste management for the European countries located in its southern region	authorities	case study on South Europe

		region, experts knowledge				
[7]	solid waste management	analysis and development of effective solid waste management and recycling programs	simulation-based decision-making and optimization framework for the analysis and development of effective solid waste management and recycling programs	WM assessment and a resource allocation optimization	authorities	simulation, US, Florida
[17]	landfill design	current knowledge of barrier systems from textbooks on landfill design and waste management	knowledge base from books about landfill design + algorithm for data processing and decision making	maximizing long-term performance and service life of the landfill	authorities and companies	no
[14]	reduce plastic waste generation	Data on Generation and disposal of Plastic Waste in South Korea	Plastic Waste Control Plan (PWCP), Government of South Korea conceptual framework	reduce plastic waste generation and increase plastic waste disposal	authorities, government level	no data
[15]	zero-waste management	zero-waste management	analyzing an extensive existing study available in the research domain	conceptual framework	authorities and companies	no
[8]	municipal solid waste, food waste	Municipal Solid Waste, Food Waste	Literature on the topic	integration	authorities	theoretical case study
[9]	municipal solid waste	municipal solid waste	Existing databases and governmental reports were reviewed to compile 1720 records of MSW generation, composition, management practices, and socioeconomic contexts for 219 countries and 410 cities	Multivariate linear regression and additive models were built to relate MSW generation, composition, and recovery rates to demographics, economic development, and climate patterns of cities and regions	authorities	simulation, US, Florida

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Appendix 2. Testing questionnaire

DSF Step №	DSF Step	Feedback form
1	Framework Guide	What is unclear and should be explained better?
		What should be added?
2	Context	What is unclear and needs additional comments?
		What context parameters should be added? What is the purpose of adding these context parameters?
		What context parameters should be removed? Why?
3	Goals	What is unclear and needs additional comments?
		What goals should be added? Why?
		What goals should be removed / renamed / combined? Why?
4	Challenges	What is unclear and needs additional comments?
		What challenges should be added? Why?
		What challenges should be removed / renamed / combined? Why?
5	Recommendations	Which recommendations are unclear? What should be added / explained better? (dropdown list)
		What additional recommendations can be given? (add recommendations in the format [Challenge]: [Recommendation (title, recommendation text, references)])
		What recommendations are incorrect/inaccurate? Please provide a rationale.
		Design of the recommendations page
		(1) Is it necessary to reduce the amount of text on the page (for example, move references to literature to an expandable block)?
		(2) Do I need to add graphic information (photographs, drawings, diagrams)?
(3) Links to similar systems with features or designs that could make this framework better. Please add comments on what I should pay attention to in the specified system.		
	General framework feedback	

Appendix 3. Context parameters of the city and WM system

Context parameters Category	Context parameters Sub-category	Options
Basic city context	City size and population	<input type="checkbox"/> Megalopolis (> 10 million residents) <input type="checkbox"/> Conurbation (3-10 million residents) <input type="checkbox"/> Metropolis (1-3 million residents) <input type="checkbox"/> City (large city) (300 000 - 1 million residents) <input type="checkbox"/> Prefecture (medium city) (100 000 - 300 000 residents) <input type="checkbox"/> Borough (small city) (10 000 - 100 000 residents) <input type="checkbox"/> Medium town (1 000 - 10 000 residents) <input type="checkbox"/> Small town (> 1 000 residents)
	Climate	<input type="checkbox"/> Tropical (every month of the year with an average temperature of 18 °C or higher, with significant precipitation) <input type="checkbox"/> Dry (no month with an average temperature greater than 10 °C) <input type="checkbox"/> Temperate (the coldest month averaging between 0 °C and 18 °C and at least one month averaging above 10 °C) <input type="checkbox"/> Continental (at least one month averaging below 0 °C and at least one month averaging above 10 °C) <input type="checkbox"/> Polar (every month of the year with an average temperature below 10 °C)
Existing Waste Management (WM) infrastructure	Mark the physical infrastructure for waste management that the city has	<input type="checkbox"/> Garbage bins <input type="checkbox"/> Waste trucks <input type="checkbox"/> Points of intermediate waste storage <input type="checkbox"/> Control Station (dispatchers) <input type="checkbox"/> Plant / Factory: Waste disposal <input type="checkbox"/> Plant / Factory: Waste recycling <input type="checkbox"/> Plant / Factory: Waste valorization (mechanical, physical, thermal) <input type="checkbox"/> Plant / Factory: Waste treatment <input type="checkbox"/> Point of waste collection (Dump) <input type="checkbox"/> Pipes for transporting waste <input type="checkbox"/> All of the above <input type="checkbox"/> None of the above
	Is there a separate	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No

	waste collection in the city?	
	Is separate waste collection available in all areas of the city?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Separate collection of some types of waste is everywhere, separate collection of some types of waste is not available in all areas <input type="checkbox"/> Separate waste collection does not work in all areas of the city
WM technologies	What city level WM services are used in the city?	<input type="checkbox"/> Smart garbage bins <input type="checkbox"/> IoT devices on garbage trucks <input type="checkbox"/> IoT devices for waste sorting <input type="checkbox"/> Waste classification / segregation <input type="checkbox"/> Optimization of the planning of waste collection operations: Route planning <input type="checkbox"/> Optimization of the planning of waste collection operations: Route optimization <input type="checkbox"/> Optimization of the planning of waste collection operations: Scheduling <input type="checkbox"/> Optimization of the planning of waste collection operations: SGB positioning <input type="checkbox"/> Optimization of the planning of waste collection operations: Door-to-Door Garbage Collection <input type="checkbox"/> Ondemand emptying of housing waste bins <input type="checkbox"/> User support: City Dashboard (Map) <input type="checkbox"/> User support: Notifications for drivers <input type="checkbox"/> User support: Information support for other stakeholders <input type="checkbox"/> User support: Complaints and revues for citizens <input type="checkbox"/> Environment: Measure Environmental parameters <input type="checkbox"/> Environment: Minimize Carbon Emissions <input type="checkbox"/> Monitoring the quantity and quality of household waste using technologies <input type="checkbox"/> All of the above <input type="checkbox"/> None of the above

	<p>What Smart Garbage Bin (SGB) level WM services are used in the city?</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="checkbox"/> Monitoring: Show bins on the Map <input type="checkbox"/> Monitoring: Video monitoring <input type="checkbox"/> Monitoring: Fill level <input type="checkbox"/> Monitoring: Weight <input type="checkbox"/> Monitoring: GPS <input type="checkbox"/> Monitoring: Temperature <input type="checkbox"/> Monitoring: Humidity <input type="checkbox"/> Monitoring: Moisture <input type="checkbox"/> Monitoring: Gas (CO, NO2) <input type="checkbox"/> Monitoring: Air quality <input type="checkbox"/> Monitoring: SGB Lid control <input type="checkbox"/> Monitoring: Metal <input type="checkbox"/> Monitoring: Rain <input type="checkbox"/> Monitoring: Person detection <input type="checkbox"/> Monitoring: Existence of harmful materials and gases <input type="checkbox"/> Identification and classification: SGB identification <input type="checkbox"/> Identification and classification: Waste type identification <input type="checkbox"/> Identification and classification: Individual waste amount <input type="checkbox"/> Identification and classification: Person identification: Waste classification / segregation (SGB level) <input type="checkbox"/> All of the above <input type="checkbox"/> None of the above
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Stakeholders	Mark primary and secondary stakeholders, involved in waste management process	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="checkbox"/> Primary Stakeholders: Citizen <input type="checkbox"/> Primary Stakeholders: Driver <input type="checkbox"/> Primary Stakeholders: Waste collection company <input type="checkbox"/> Primary Stakeholders: Dispatcher of waste collection company <input type="checkbox"/> Primary Stakeholders: Janitor <input type="checkbox"/> Primary Stakeholders: City administration <input type="checkbox"/> Primary Stakeholders: Municipality/ District administration <input type="checkbox"/> Primary Stakeholders: Waste trucks owning company <input type="checkbox"/> Primary Stakeholders: Waste department <input type="checkbox"/> Primary Stakeholders: Waste disposal organization <input type="checkbox"/> Primary Stakeholders: Waste recycling company <input type="checkbox"/> Primary Stakeholders: Waste treating company <input type="checkbox"/> Primary Stakeholders: Dump (Dump manager) <input type="checkbox"/> Secondary Stakeholders: Police <input type="checkbox"/> Secondary Stakeholders: Firefighters <input type="checkbox"/> Secondary Stakeholders: Municipal corporation <input type="checkbox"/> Secondary Stakeholders: Production center <input type="checkbox"/> Secondary Stakeholders: Health/environmental emergencies management organization <input type="checkbox"/> Secondary Stakeholders: Farmer <input type="checkbox"/> Secondary Stakeholders: Volunteer <input type="checkbox"/> Secondary Stakeholders: Recycling industry <input type="checkbox"/> Secondary Stakeholders: Disposal industry <input type="checkbox"/> Secondary Stakeholders: Food industry <input type="checkbox"/> Secondary Stakeholders: Healthcare <input type="checkbox"/> Secondary Stakeholders: Research <input type="checkbox"/> Secondary Stakeholders: Environment protection and related organizations <input type="checkbox"/> Secondary Stakeholders: Tourism industry
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Financial aspects	What is the city's annual budget for tasks related to waste management? (€)	[Numeric]
	What is the annual city budget for solving current waste management related problems? (€)	[Numeric]
	What is the the average income of the citizens? (€)	[Numeric]
Residents awareness	Level of stakeholders Awareness and Engagement in Waste Management activities	<p>[Rating from 1 to 5, where:</p> <p>1 — Unaware — This is the lowest level of stakeholder engagement. Unaware stakeholders are not aware of the activity and its potential impacts.</p> <p>2 — Resistant — This level of stakeholder engagement defines those who are aware of the activity and potential impacts, but are resistant to change or hesitant to get involved.</p> <p>3 — Neutral — These stakeholders are aware of the activities but are neither supportive nor resistant.</p> <p>4 — Supportive — Supportive stakeholders are aware of the activity and its potential impacts and are supportive of change and willing to consider doing what they can to aid a activity.</p> <p>5 — Leading — This is the highest level of engagement. These stakeholders are fully aware of the activity and its impacts and are actively engaged to ensure the activity is successful.]</p>
	What is the level of education of the residence?	<input type="checkbox"/> More than 50% with basic education <input type="checkbox"/> More than 50% with higher education <input type="checkbox"/> 50% with basic education and 50% with higher education

Appendix 4. The goals, challenges and it's KPIs

Goals	Goals KPIs	Challenges	Challenges KPIs
Clean streets	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Number of citizens' complaints per month • The number of pieces of garbage per 10 square meters • Your KPI name 	Not enough trash cans	-
		Streets not cleaned often enough by janitors	
		Low level of environmental awareness among residents	
		Insufficiently frequent of garbage trucks movement	
		Poor cleanliness of the area around waste containers	
		Overflow of waste containers	
		Birds scattering garbage	
Clean public places, such as parks, car parks or shopping areas	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Number of citizens' complaints per month • The number of pieces of garbage per 10 square meters • Your KPI name 	Not enough trash cans	-
		Public places not cleaned often enough by janitors	
		Low level of environmental awareness among residents	
		Insufficiently frequent of garbage trucks movement	
		Poor cleanliness of the area around waste containers	
		Overflow of waste containers	

		Birds scattering garbage	
Improve the environmental situation in the city	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Number of citizens' complaints per month Your KPI name 	Air quality	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Air Quality Index
		Garbage on the streets	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Number of citizens' complaints per month The number of pieces of garbage per 10 square meters
		Garbage in public places	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Number of citizens' complaints per month The number of pieces of garbage per 10 square meters
		Unauthorized garbage dumps	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Number of citizens' complaints per month
		Insufficiently frequent of garbage trucks movement	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Number of citizens' complaints per month
		Hazardous waste is not sorted	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Kilograms of sorted hazardous waste per month
Budget savings	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Total costs (€) Saved costs (€) Your KPI name 	Garbage collection with garbage trucks (gasoline, drivers' salaries)	-
		Janitor salaries	
		Waste sorting costs	
		Waste processing costs	
		Waste disposal costs	

Improving the waste management logistics	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Number of citizens' complaints per month Number of rides per month Your KPI name 	Garbage is taken out irregularly	-
		Empty runs	
		Garbage trucks obstruct traffic	
		Different types of garbage are collected by different companies	
Increasing stakeholder awareness	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Level of stakeholders Awareness and Engagement in Waste Management activities (1- Unaware, 2- Resistant, 3- Neutral, 4- Supportive, 5- Leading) Your KPI name 	Waste collection company (Drivers)	-
		Waste collection company (Dispatchers)	
		Janitors	
		Authorities / City administration / District administration	
		Waste department	
		Waste disposal organization	
		Waste recycling company	
		Waste treating company	
Introduction / Improvement of waste processing	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Number of kg of waste processed per month Your KPI name 	Lack of infrastructure	-
		Incorrect waste sorting	
Improvement of bio-waste processing	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Number of kg of bio-waste processed in the city per month Your KPI name 	Lack of infrastructure	-
		Incorrect waste sorting	
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Costs saved per month (€) 	Household waste sorting	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Costs saved per month (€)

Cost effective technology solutions for SWM	• Your KPI name		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Number of kg of each type of waste sorted correctly per month (Mixed waste, Bio-waste, Plastic, Carton, Paper, Glass, Metal, Hazardous waste, Fabric)
		Household waste logistics	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Costs saved per month (€) • Number of citizens' complaints per month • Number of empty runs per month
		Household waste sorting of bio-waste	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Costs saved per month (€) • Number of kg of bio-waste sorted correctly per month
		Household waste logistics of bio-waste	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Costs saved per month (€) • Number of citizens' complaints per month • Number of empty runs per month • Smell, numeric (Data from gas / air quality sensor)
		Air quality	-

		Waste processing	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Costs saved per month (€) • Number of kg of waste processed per month
		Citizens awareness, engagement and motivation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Costs saved per month (€) • Number of kg of each type of waste sorted incorrectly per month (Mixed waste, Bio-waste, Plastic, Carton, Paper, Glass, Metal, Hazardous waste, Fabric) • Number of kg of each type of waste sorted correctly per month (Mixed waste, Bio-waste, Plastic, Carton, Paper, Glass, Metal, Hazardous waste, Fabric)
Increase the waste recycling level	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Your KPI name 	Lack of infrastructure	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Number of kg of each type of waste recycled per month (Mixed waste, Bio-waste, Plastic, Carton, Paper, Glass, Metal, Hazardous waste, Fabric)

			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Number of kg of each type of waste per month (Mixed waste, Bio-waste, Plastic, Carton, Paper, Glass, Metal, Hazardous waste, Fabric)
		Incorrect waste sorting	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Number of kg of each type of waste sorted incorrectly per month (Mixed waste, Bio-waste, Plastic, Carton, Paper, Glass, Metal, Hazardous waste, Fabric) Number of kg of each type of waste sorted correctly per month (Mixed waste, Bio-waste, Plastic, Carton, Paper, Glass, Metal, Hazardous waste, Fabric)
		Problems with citizens participation in waste reduction, recycling, other sustainable WM practices	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Number of participants in WM practices per month
		Problems with citizens willingness to pay for new	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Amount of payments per month (€)

		sustainable WM services	
Electronical waste (E-waste) sorting and disposal improvement	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Number of kg of e-waste sorted correctly per month Your KPI name 	Making e-waste sorting and disposal easier and accessible	-
		Incorrect e-waste sorting	
		Low citizens motivation	
Improving the logistics and way of operation regarding bio-waste	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Number of citizens' complaints per month Smell, numeric (Data from gas / air quality sensor) Your KPI name 	Bio-waste is taken out irregularly	-
		Smell	
		Spread of diseases due to untimely disposal of waste	
Waste sorting	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Number of kg of each type of waste per month (Mixed waste, Bio-waste, Plastic, Carton, Paper, Glass, Metal, Hazardous waste, Fabric) Your KPI name 	Sorting of household waste: Incorrect waste sorting	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Number of kg of waste sorted incorrectly per month (Mixed waste, Bio-waste, Plastic, Carton, Paper, Glass, Metal, Hazardous waste, Fabric) Number of kg of waste sorted correctly per month (Mixed waste, Bio-waste, Plastic, Carton, Paper, Glass, Metal, Hazardous waste, Fabric)
		Sorting of household waste: Residents do not sort all types of garbage	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Number of kg of waste sorted incorrectly per month (Mixed

			waste, Bio-waste, Plastic, Carton, Paper, Glass, Metal, Hazardous waste, Fabric)
		Introduction of sorting of more types of waste	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Number of kg of each type of waste sorted correctly per month (Mixed waste, Bio-waste, Plastic, Carton, Paper, Glass, Metal, Hazardous waste, Fabric) • Number of waste types sorted in each district of the city
Waste minimization	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Number of kg of each type of waste per month (Mixed waste, Bio-waste, Plastic, Carton, Paper, Glass, Metal, Hazardous waste, Fabric) • Your KPI name 	Low citizens motivation	
		Low citizens awareness	
Increasing environmental awareness, engagement and motivation of citizens	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Level of stakeholders Awareness, Motivation and Engagement in Waste Management activities (1-Unaware, 2- 	Incorrect household waste sorting	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Number of kg of each type of waste sorted incorrectly per month (Mixed waste, Bio-waste, Plastic, Carton, Paper, Glass, Metal,

	Resistant, 3- Neutral, 4- Supportive, 5- Leading) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Your KPI name 		Hazardous waste, Fabric) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Number of kg of each type of waste sorted correctly per month (Mixed waste, Bio-waste, Plastic, Carton, Paper, Glass, Metal, Hazardous waste, Fabric)
		Residents do not sort all types of garbage	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Number of kg of each type of waste sorted correctly per month
		Residence do not sort waste at all	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Number of kg of each type of waste sorted correctly per month (Mixed waste, Bio-waste, Plastic, Carton, Paper, Glass, Metal, Hazardous waste, Fabric)
		Garbage on the streets	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Number of citizens' complaints per month The number of pieces of garbage per 10 square meters
		Garbage in public places	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Number of citizens' complaints per month

			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The number of pieces of garbage per 10 square meters
		Garbage storage is far away from home	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Number of kg of each type of waste sorted correctly per month (Mixed waste, Bio-waste, Plastic, Carton, Paper, Glass, Metal, Hazardous waste, Fabric) • Number of citizens' complaints per month
		Don't get enough knowledge/education of waste sorting	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Number of kg of each type of waste sorted correctly per month (Mixed waste, Bio-waste, Plastic, Carton, Paper, Glass, Metal, Hazardous waste, Fabric)
		Takes extra time and effort to sort waste properly	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Number of kg of each type of waste sorted correctly per month (Mixed waste, Bio-waste, Plastic, Carton, Paper, Glass, Metal, Hazardous waste, Fabric)

		Lack of awareness of how excess waste affects negatively on the environmental and human wellbeing	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Number of kg of each type of waste sorted correctly per month (Mixed waste, Bio-waste, Plastic, Carton, Paper, Glass, Metal, Hazardous waste, Fabric)
		Lack of information on points for separate collection of some types of waste	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Number of kg of each type of waste sorted correctly per month (Mixed waste, Bio-waste, Plastic, Carton, Paper, Glass, Metal, Hazardous waste, Fabric) • Number of citizens' complaints per month
		Lack of information on the rules for waste sorting	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Number of kg of each type of waste sorted correctly per month (Mixed waste, Bio-waste, Plastic, Carton, Paper, Glass, Metal, Hazardous waste, Fabric) •
		Problems with citizens participation in waste reduction,	-

		recycling, sustainable practices	other WM	
		Problems citizens willingness to pay for sustainable services	with new WM	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Amount of payments per month (€)

Appendix 5. The scenario testing log

Framework guide

Feedback form

What is unclear and should be explained better?:
{Empty}

What should be added?:
{Empty}

Context

Basic city context

City size and population: Megalopolis (> 10 million residents)
Climate: Continental (at least one month averaging below 0 °C and at least one month averaging above 10 °C)

Existing Waste Management (WM) infrastructure

Mark the physical infrastructure for waste management that the city has:
Garbage bins, Waste trucks, Points of intermediate waste storage, Control Station (dispatchers), Plant / Factory: Waste disposal, Plant / Factory: Waste recycling, Point of waste collection (Dump)
Is there a separate waste collection in the city?: Yes
Is separate waste collection available in all areas of the city?: Yes

WM technologies

What city level WM services are used in the city?: Smart garbage bins, IoT devices on garbage trucks, Optimization of the planning of waste collection operations: Scheduling, Optimization of the planning of waste collection operations: Door-to-Door Garbage Collection, User support: City Dashboard (Map)
What Smart Garbage Bin (SGB) level WM services are used in the city?:
Monitoring: Show bins on the Map, Monitoring: Fill level , Monitoring: Weight , Monitoring: GPS

Stakeholders

Mark primary and secondary stakeholders, involved in waste management process: {Empty}

Financial aspects

What is the city's annual budget for tasks related to waste management? (€): {Empty}
What is the annual city budget for solving current waste management related problems? (€): {Empty}
What is the the average income of the citizens? (€): {Empty}

Residents awareness

Level of stakeholders Awareness and Engagement in Waste Management activities : 3

What is the level of education of the residence?: More than 50% with higher education

Feedback form

What is unclear and needs additional comments?:
{Empty}

What context parameters should be added? What is the purpose of adding these context parameters?:
{Empty}

What context parameters should be removed? Why?:
{Empty}

Goals

What goals do you want to achieve by modernizing the waste management system in the city?

Clean streets: Yes
Clean streets KPI

Current status and KPIs:
Current status and KPIs

1
-

Number of citizens' complaints per month: 283
Number of citizens' complaints per month : 100

2
-

The number of pieces of garbage per 10 square meters: 6
The number of pieces of garbage per 10 square meters: 1

3
-

Your KPI

Your KPI name: {Empty}
Your KPI value: {Empty}

Your KPI value: {Empty}

Clean public places, such as parks, car parks or shopping areas: No
Improve the environmental situation in the city: No

Budget savings: No
Improving the waste management logistics: Yes
Improving the waste management logistics KPI

Current status and KPIs:
Current status and KPIs

1
-

Number of citizens' complaints per month: 389

Number of citizens' complaints per month: 100

2

-

Number of rides per month : 1908

Number of rides per month : 500

3

-

Your KPI name: {Empty}

Your KPI value: {Empty}

Your KPI value: {Empty}

Increasing stakeholder awareness: No

Introduction / Improvement of waste processing : No

Improvement of bio-waste processing: No

Cost effective technology solutions for SWM: No

Increase the waste recycling level: No

Electronical waste (E-waste) sorting and disposal improvement : No

Improving the logistics and way of operation regarding bio-waste : No

Waste sorting: No

Waste minimization: No

Increasing environmental awareness, engagement and motivation of citizens:

No

Feedback form

What is unclear and needs additional comments?:

{Empty}

What goals should be added? Why?:

{Empty}

What goals should be removed / renamed / combined? Why?:

{Empty}

Challenges

What are the problems with the cleanliness of the streets in the city?

Not enough trash cans: Yes

Streets not cleaned often enough by janitors: No

Low level of environmental awareness among residents: No

Insufficiently frequent of garbage trucks movement: No

Poor cleanliness of the area around waste containers: No

Overflow of waste containers: Yes

Birds scattering garbage: No

What are the logistical problems associated with garbage collection in the city?

Garbage is taken out irregularly: Yes

Empty runs: Yes

Garbage trucks obstruct traffic: No

Different types of garbage are collected by different companies: No

Feedback form

What is unclear and needs additional comments?:

{Empty}

What challenges should be added? Why?:

{Empty}

What challenges should be removed / renamed / combined? Why?:

{Empty}

Recommendations

Optimize the planning of waste collection operations (trash cans)

Optimize the planning of waste collection operations (trash cans):

- Garbage bins positioning optimization
- Add garbage bins

Recommendations based on your city infrastructure and services

You can use the garbage bins positioning optimization algorithms and services. Optimization can be based on data on:

- the fullness of garbage bins (use SGB fill level monitoring sensor)
- a map of the city with the current location of the garbage bins (use GPS sensors on SGBs)
- data on empty runs of garbage trucks (use IoT devices on garbage trucks)
- the routes of the garbage trucks

The Garbage bins positioning optimization can be supplemented with a Garbage truck route optimization service.

- a map of the city with the current location of the garbage bins (use a City dashboard / map)

Additional services and infrastructure

To improve the functioning of the Garbage bins position optimization service, we recommend supplementing the city infrastructure and services by adding:

- Complaints and revues for citizens

In some cases, in addition to garbage bins positioning optimization, it is necessary to add additional garbage bins.

Using this service will help solve problems with garbage in the streets and public places, as well as help with a lack of janitors.

Read more

You can read more about developing and implementing the proposed services in the following references:

- V. Kalyuzhnyy, M. Costa, P. Silva, and J. Santos, "Smart City IoT System - CollectMyWaste," 2020, doi: 10.1109/ISMSIT50672.2020.9255271
- Y. Bevis Jinila, M. Shahzad Alam, and P. Dayal Singh, "Cloud-Based Scheme for Household Garbage Collection in Urban Areas," 2019, doi: 10.1007/978-981-13-1882-5_47
- M. I. Zahur, M. S. Rahman, A. Akther, and K. M. Alam, "An IoT Based Green Waste Management System for Bangladesh," 2019, doi: 10.1109/ICASERT.2019.8934475
- Á. Lozano Murciego, G. Villarrubia González, A. López Barriuso, D. Hernández de la Iglesia, and J. Revuelta Herrero, "Multi agent gathering waste system," Adv. Distrib. Comput. Artif. Intell. J., 2015, doi: 10.14201/ADCAIJ201544922

- S. & R. Saeidi, A., Aghamohamadi-Bosjin, "An integrated model for management of hazardous waste in a smart city with a sustainable approach," *Env. Dev Sustain*, 2020, doi: 10.1007/s10668-020-01048-7

Smart Garbage Bin (SGB) fill level monitoring

Recommendations based on your city infrastructure and services SGB fill level monitoring

Use fill level monitoring sensor (Ultrasonic / Optical / Infrared) on SGB. We recommend to use Ultrasonic sensor for SGB fill level measurements. Using this service will help solve problems with cleanliness of streets and public places, waste logistics (waste trucks routing and empty runs), air quality (lower emissions by solving problem of empty runs and timely removal of bio-waste by (additionally) using additional air quality sensors and / or gas sensor).

Read more

You can read more about developing and implementing the proposed services in the following references:

1. SWM Systems with SGB-related Services:

Ultrasonic:

- S. K. Memon, F. Karim Shaikh, N. A. Mahoto, and A. Aziz Memon, "IoT based smart garbage monitoring collection system using WeMos Ultrasonic sensors," 2019, doi: 10.1109/ICOMET.2019.8673526
- T. Ali, M. Irfan, A. S. Alwadie, and A. Glowacz, "IoT-Based Smart Waste Bin Monitoring and Municipal Solid Waste Management System for Smart Cities," *Arab. J. Sci. Eng.*, 2020, doi: 10.1007/s13369-020-04637-w

Optical:

- M. Falch and M. Maestrini, "Public Private Partnership in Smart city waste management - a Business Case," in 2019 CTTE-FITCE: Smart Cities & Information and Communication Technology (CTTE-FITCE), 2019, pp. 1-6, doi: 10.1109/CTTE-FITCE.2019.8894820
- M. J. Beliatis, H. Mansour, S. Nagy, A. Aagaard, and M. Presser, "Digital waste management using LoRa network a business case from lab to fab," 2018, doi: 10.1109/GIOTS.2018.8534562

Infrared:

- A. S. Bharadwaj, R. Rego, and A. Chowdhury, "IoT based solid waste management system: A conceptual approach with an architectural solution as a smart city application," 2017, doi: 10.1109/INDICON.2016.7839147

2. SGBs:

Ultrasonic:

- R. Kansara, P. Bhojani, and J. Chauhan, "Smart waste management for segregating different types of wastes," 2019, doi: 10.1007/978-981-13-1402-5_3
- T. Addabbo et al., "A LoRa-based IoT Sensor Node for Waste Management Based on a Customized Ultrasonic Transceiver," 2019, doi: 10.1109/SAS.2019.8705980

Ultrasonic + Infrared:

- G. S. Rohit, M. B. Chandra, S. Saha, and D. Das, "Smart Dual Dustbin Model for Waste Management in Smart Cities," 2018, doi: 10.1109/I2CT.2018.8529600
- K. N. C. Tiwari, "Waste management using solar smart bin," in 2017 International Conference on Energy, Communication, Data Analytics and Soft Computing (ICECDS), 2017, pp. 1123-1126

Infrared:

- Chandan T.V., Kumari R.C., Tekam R., Shruti B.V., "Smart Waste Monitoring Using Wireless Sensor Networks," in Emerging Research in Computing, Information, Communication and Applications, 2019, pp. 363-369

Optimize the planning of waste collection operations (Trucks / Drivers)

Optimize the planning of waste collection operations (Trucks / Drivers):

- Route planning
- Route optimization
- Scheduling

Recommendations based on your city infrastructure and services

Route planning and optimization may involve automatic route planning (preliminary or real-time) based on:

- City Dashboard (Map)
- IoT devices on garbage trucks
- GPS on SGB
- SGB Fill level Monitoring sensor

Scheduling service provides automatic scheduling for drivers.

Using this service will help solve problems with logistics (no empty runs, efficient waste disposal system), cleanliness of the city (with timely waste disposal), save the city budget (minimize driver work time, reduce the number of janitors, reduce fuel costs), city ecology and air quality (lower emissions by solving problem of empty runs and timely removal of bio-waste by (additionally) using additional air quality sensors and / or gas sensor).

Read more

You can read more about developing and implementing the proposed services in the following references:

- P. J. Shah, T. Anagnostopoulos, A. Zaslavsky, "A stochastic optimization framework for planning of waste collection and value recovery operations in smart and sustainable cities," Waste Manag., vol. 78, pp. 104 - 114
- T. Anagnostopoulos, A. Zaslavsky, A. Medvedev, and S. Khoruzhnicov, "Top - k Query Based Dynamic Scheduling for IoT-enabled Smart City Waste Collection," 2015, doi: 10.1109/MDM.2015.25
- T. Anagnostopoulos, K. Kolomvatsos, C. Anagnostopoulos, A. Zaslavsky, and S. Hadjiefthymiades, "Assessing dynamic models for high priority waste collection in smart cities," J. Syst. Softw., 2015, doi: 10.1016/j.jss.2015.08.049
- T. Anagnostopoulos, A. Zaslavsky, S. Georgiou, and S. Khoruzhnikov, "High capacity trucks serving as mobile depots for waste collection in iot-enabled smart cities," 2015, doi: 10.1007/978-3-319-23126-6_8T.
- Anagnostopoulos, A. Zaslavsky, I. Sosunova, P. Fedchenkov, A. Medvedev, K. Ntalianis, C. Skourlas, A. Rybin, "A stochastic multi-agent system for Internet of Things-enabled waste management in smart cities," Waste Manag. Res., vol. 36, pp. 1113-1121, 2018, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1177/0734242X18783843>

City dashboard (map)

City dashboard (map)

A map with waste management infrastructure.

Can be used for citizens: to mark on the map the nearest collection points for various types of waste. Or for drivers, to mark waste bins and waste collection routes.

Using this service will help solve problems with lack of waste collection infrastructure or low citizens awareness of the placement of nearest waste collection points of some rare types of waste (for example, old clothes, batteries).

Read more

You can read more about developing and implementing the proposed services in the following references:

- K. Pardini, J. J. P. C. Rodrigues, O. Diallo, A. K. Das, V. H. C. de Albuquerque, and S. A. Kozlov, "A smart waste management solution geared towards citizens," *Sensors (Switzerland)*, 2020, doi: 10.3390/s20082380
- T. Anagnostopoulos, A. Zaslavsky, I. Sosunova, P. Fedchenkov, A. Medvedev, K. Ntalianis, C. Skourlas, A. Rybin, "A stochastic multi-agent system for Internet of Things-enabled waste management in smart cities," *Waste Manag. Res.*, vol. 36, pp. 1113-1121, 2018, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1177/0734242X18783843>
- L. Abbatecola, M. P. Fanti, A. M. Mangini, and W. Ukovich, "A Decision Support Approach for Postal Delivery and Waste Collection Services," *IEEE Trans. Autom. Sci. Eng.*, 2016, doi: 10.1109/TASE.2016.2570121
- Á. L. Murcieto, G. V. González, A. L. Barriuso, D. H. de La Iglesia, J. R. Herrero, and J. F. De Paz Santana, "Smart waste collection platform based on WSN and route optimization," 2016, doi: 10.1007/978-3-319-40159-1_11
- Á. Lozano, J. Caridad, J. F. De Paz, G. V. González, and J. Bajo, "Smart waste collection system with low consumption LoRaWAN nodes and route optimization," *Sensors (Switzerland)*, 2018, doi: 10.3390/s18051465

On-demand emptying of garbage bins

On-demand emptying of garbage bins

Using this service will help solve problems with logistics (less empty runs), air quality (less emissions), costs savings (less gasoline, drivers working hours).

Feedback form

Which recommendations are unclear? What should be added / explained better?

:

{Empty}

What additional recommendations can be given? (add recommendations in the format [Challenge]: [Recommendation (title, recommendation text, references)]):

{Empty}

What recommendations are incorrect/inaccurate? Please provide a rationale.:

{Empty}

Is it necessary to reduce the amount of text on the page (for example, move references to literature to an expandable block)?:

{Empty}

Do I need to add graphic information (photographs, drawings, diagrams)?:

{Empty}

Links to similar systems with features or designs that could make this framework better. Please add comments on what I should pay attention to in the specified system:

{Empty}

General framework feedback:

{Empty}